

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on the chromatographic methodology set up to draw the extract's fingerprint

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

Flagship project VINO

RM4- Don't waste the waste

DELIVERABLE D4.2

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	1 st March 2024	Initial draft	Elisabetta Tumminelli/Daniela Rossi
0.5	10 th March 2024	Draft implementation	Daniela Rossi
0.9	15 th March 2024	Draft conclusion	Daniela Rossi
1	27 th March 2024	Final review	Daniela Rossi

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Herein we report on the development of a rapid and low solvent consuming HPLC-UV/PAD analytical methodology suitable for the analysis of *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood extracts and for the quantitation of their main secondary metabolites, *E*-Resveratrol and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin. Specifically, for quantification purposes, the method was validated in terms of linearity, detection limit (DL) e quantitation limit (QL), repeatability for both the analytes.

A) Materials and Methods

In this section chemicals (e.g. standards and solvents), instruments and methodologies used (e.g. for HPLC-UV/PAD analysis and for extractions) are reported.

Plant material

One-year old lignified shoots of *Vitis Vinifera* Syrah were collected from 16 years old vines in the collection vineyards of the University of Turin (DISAFA vineyard; 45 30530 0 N, 7350320 0 E) in Grugliasco (TO), Italy on 02 February 2023. The DISAFA vineyard, planted in 2008, has a density of 4400 vines/ha and is situated 293 m above sea level in a flat area. Vines are vertically shoot positioned and trained to the Guyot pruning system. The soil composition is sandy; further details can be found in Catoni et al. (2012). Integrated agricultural management practices are applied. Syrah is grafted on SO4 (*Vitis berlandieri* x *Vitis riparia*). After collection, plant material was cleaned, cut and left to dry in a ventilated stove at 35°C until constant weight and then stored in a dark, dry place. Before extraction, plant material was finely chopped using a blade-mill (A10 IKA-Werke GmbH & Co., Staufen, Germany).

Chemicals and standards

HPLC-grade solvents (Acetonitrile and Methanol) were supplied by Merck-Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy), while analytical grade ethanol was supplied by PanReac (Barcelona, Spain). Formic acid was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). *E*-Resveratrol and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin were purchased from Merck Life Science S.r.l (Milan, Italy); *E*-piceatannol, *E*-polydatin were purchased from Extrasynthèse (Genay, France).

Instruments and methodologies

Ultrasound -assisted extraction (UAE)

Four hundred milligrams of plant material were extracted using 2 mL of methanol: water (80:20 v/v) acidified with 0.1% (v/v) acetic acid in an Elmasonic P ultrasonic bath (VWR International srl, Milano, Italy), for 1 hour. The mixture was filtered, evaporated to dryness using a Heidolph Laborota 4000 instrument (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co., Schwabach, Germany) and/or

using a Smart Evaporator C1 (Stepbio, Bologna, Italy) and then dissolved with a methanol: water (80:20 v/v) mixture, to have a final concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹. Samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m filter and placed in a vial for HPLC-UV/PAD analysis.

Microwave-assisted Extraction (MAE)

Extraction was conducted under microwave irradiation in a microwave mono-mode oven (Discover® Lab-Mate instrument, CEM Corporate, Buckingham, UK) equipped with a power and temperature controller, applying the experimental conditions already described in deliverable D4.1. Briefly, extraction conditions involve 100% EtOH as extraction solvent, a 5-minute microwave cycle at a temperature of 80°C with a microwave power of 50W, using a 20% (w/v) plant material-solvent ratio (400mg of plant material extracted using 2 mL of EtOH). Once the microwave extraction cycle was completed, the mixture was filtered, evaporated to dryness using a Heidolph Laborota 4000 instrument (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co., Schwabach, Germany) and/or using a Smart Evaporator C1 (Stepbio, Bologna, Italy) and then dissolved with methanol: water (80:20 v/v) mixture, to have a final concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹. Samples were filtered through a 0.45 μ m filter and placed in a vial for HPLC-UV/PAD analysis.

HPLC-UV/PAD analysis

All analyses were carried out using a JASCO (Jasco Europe, Cremella, Italy) bench-top HPLC system, including a quaternary pump model PU-4180, autosampler model AS-4050 with a 5 μ L loop installed on purpose, column thermostatic compartment model CO-4065, and an UV-Vis photodiode array detector (PAD) model MD-4010. The system was fully operated by the JASCO ChromNAV software (version 2.04.03) operating in Microsoft Windows 7 Professional environment. HPLC analyses were performed at 25°C using a Hibar® HR Purospher® STAR RP-18 endcapped column (2.1 mm ID x 100 mm, particle size 3 μ m), eluting with water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (B) in gradient mode, at a flow rate of 0.2 mL min⁻¹.

B) Development and optimization of the HPLC-UV/PAD method

In this section the development of a rapid and low solvent consuming HPLC-UV/PAD analytical methodology suitable for the analysis of *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood extracts and for the quantitation of their main secondary metabolites, *E*-Resveratrol and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin, is described.

Method development

To set-up the elution conditions, reference standards of *E*-Resveratrol, *E*- ϵ -Viniferin, *E*-polydatin, and *E*-piceatannol, which are the most abundant stilbenes expressed in *Vitis vinifera* wood cane, were used together with a pilot extract that was prepared by ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE), according to literature procedure¹. Briefly, plant material was extracted using methanol: water (80:20 v/v) acidified with 0.1% (v/v) acetic acid in an ultrasonic bath for one hour, using a 20% (w/v) plant material-solvent ratio. The mixture was filtered, evaporated to dryness and the crude extract was used to set-up a rapid and low-solvent consuming HPLC-UV/PAD method suitable for drawing the fingerprint of *Vitis vinifera* pruning wood extracts.

Different mobile phase compositions, applied to the columns both in isocratic and gradient mode, were investigated. The best results in terms of time of analysis, peak shape and peak resolution were achieved by eluting with water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (B) in gradient mode, starting from 5% to 40% of B in 4 min, a second gradient from 40% to 50% of B in 9 min, a third gradient up to 80% of B in 7 min which was followed by an isocratic elution phase for 5 min. The column was reconditioned by eluting from 80% of B to 5% of B in 0.1 min and with a final 15 min isocratic elution at the initial conditions (5% of B). The flow rate was 0.2 mL min⁻¹. In figure 1 the HPLC-UV/PAD profiles of the four standard stilbenes (Figure 1A, λ = 306 nm) and the crude pilot UAE extract (Figure 1B, λ = 306 nm) are reported.

¹ Nerva, L. et al.. Biol. Fertil. Soils, 2022, 58(1), 17-34

The optimized chromatographic conditions were finally exploited for drawing the fingerprint of the extract prepared applying our already developed MAE procedure (see deliverable D4.1) to one-year old lignified shoots of *Vitis vinifera* Syrah. The HPLC-UV/PAD profile ($\lambda = 306$ nm) of the crude MAE extract is reported in figure 2.

Figure 2

As shown in Figure 2, the analytical method developed is suitable for drawing the fingerprint of the MAE pruning wood extract. Moreover, it appears clear that *E*-Resveratrol and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin are the most abundant secondary metabolites present in the MAE extract. Accordingly, the method was validated for the quantitation of these two metabolites.

Method Validation

To properly quantify *E*-Resveratrol and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin present in pruning wood extracts, the HPLC-UV/PAD method developed was validated in terms of linearity, detection limit (DL) e quantitation limit (QL), repeatability, according to the ICH Q2(R2) and USFDA guidelines on validation of analytical procedures.

Linearity, Detection Limit (DL) e Quantitation Limit (QL)

Stock solutions of *E*-Resveratrol ($c \sim 1 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) *E*- ϵ -Viniferin ($c \sim 0.83 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) were prepared in methanol: water (80:20 v/v) mixture. The calibration curves were then built through ten points, each replicated three times, in the range of 800-0.10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and of 726-0.10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for *E*-Resveratrol *E*- ϵ -Viniferin, respectively. The method response function was linear within the concentration range investigated for both *E*-Resveratrol ($3 \cdot 10^7 x + 157104$; $R^2 = 0.9974$) and *E*- ϵ -Viniferin ($y = 1 \cdot 10^7 x + 40138$, $R^2 = 0.9992$) (Figure 3). DL and QL were also calculated (*E*-resveratrol: DL of 0.63 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, QL of 1.93 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$; *E*- ϵ -Viniferin: DL= 0.70 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, QL= 2.12 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) through the calibration curves.

Figure 3

Repeatability

The repeatability of the HPLC-UV/PAD method was verified by performing 10 determinations at the test concentration of $250 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and $259 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for *E-Resveratrol* and *E-ε-Viniferin*, respectively. Both peak area and retention times were evaluated, furnishing for both the analytes a % RSD <2, that indicates the suitability of the system for the intended application.